

FACTORS OF FORMATION OF ETHNO-CULTURAL COMPETENCE IN STUDENTS

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Abstract:... in our article, the factors of formation of ethnocultural competence in students, the processes that affect them and the social influences that move them, to achieve our great state, our great future, intelligent, enlightened, at the same time, its past, great values, nation The need to educate perfect people who are proud of themselves and believe in the future, and the fact that it is the duty of professors and teachers to establish the theoretical basis of social and humanitarian sciences taught in all universities and to carry them out in connection with our daily life, is explained in detail.

Keywords: culture, patriotism, ethnoculture, ethnography, ethnology, ethnocultural competence, cognitive factor, moral factor, motivational factor.

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ФАКТОРЫ ФОРМИРОВАНИЯ ЭТНОКУЛЬТУРНОЙ КОМПЕТЕНЦИИ СТУДЕНТОВ

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Abstract:... в нашей статье рассмотрены факторы формирования этнокультурной компетентности у студентов, процессы, влияющие на них, и социальные влияния, которые их двигают, на достижение нашего великого государства, нашего великого будущего, интеллигентного, просвещенного, в то же время, своего прошлого. , великие ценности, нация Необходимость воспитать совершенных людей, гордящихся собой и верящих в будущее, и то, что обязанностью профессором и преподавателем является создание теоретических основ социально-гуманитарных наук, преподаваемых во всех вузах и выполнять их в связи с нашей повседневной жизнью, подробно объясняется.

Keywords: культура, патриотизм, этнокультура, этнография, этнология, этнокультурная компетентность, познавательный фактор, нравственный фактор, мотивационный фактор.

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First President I.A. Karimov said, "It is urgent to study the history and culture, geography and economy of the Motherland, as well as our ancient traditions. "Ethnoculture should be considered as an important political task in educational systems from preschool age to higher educational institutions" [1]. Therefore, in order to achieve our great country and great future, it is necessary to educate intelligent, enlightened, perfect people who are proud of their past, great values, nation and believe in the future. Education of a perfect personality is the theoretical

basis of social and humanitarian sciences taught in all universities, and it is the duty of professors and teachers to carry them out in connection with our daily life.

In this way, first of all, it is important to explain the following words that help explain culture and its components.

The word "Culture" comes from the Arabic word Medina. The interpretation of the word culture, which comes in the meaning of the city, is focused on two types of people's life, that is, peoples living in the nomadic steppes and peoples living in the city and living a lifestyle typical of the city.

It is known that the concept of culture has a broad meaning and is expressed in a certain level of historical development of society and man, in various forms of people's life and activities, as well as in the material and spiritual wealth created by them. Also, culture is a universal phenomenon, equal to all.

The concept of ethnoculture reflects the formation and development of the culture of clan, people, and nation in the historical process. Traditional culture is manifested as an important part of ethnic culture that is formed, tested and passed down from generation to generation.

Ethnocultural concepts have been formed as a historical process and have shown certain achievements and shortcomings over time.

In terms of ethnological quality, the society has passed its spiritual and cultural life from generation to generation and created the ground for its future. Students are given the understanding that conscious study of the past culture, without learning it, there is no basis for using the cultural heritage for the development of the society. Islam is the heritage of national spirituality and culture. It is known that the territory of Central Asia is the center of formation of material and spiritual culture.

Ethnography is a branch of science that studies the origin, material and spiritual culture of peoples, and talks about people's lifestyle, culture and traditions. The term ethnology is also used in the field of social sciences.

The term ethnology is derived from the ancient Greek words "ethnos" and "people" and means folklore. In some countries, ethnography, cultural or social anthropology, folk studies are still used together with the term ethnology.

Therefore, it is important to study the traditional folk culture as a whole and multifaceted phenomenon, to determine its structure, main manifestations and forms. Therefore, based on the classification of culture, it is a component of the system of ethnoculture and traditional folk culture, which is a component of it. The components of traditional folk culture are folk wisdom, philosophy, faith, pedagogy, customs, oral creativity, folk games, recreation culture, cooking, national costumes, architecture, folk art, folk can be seen in many areas such as medicine, folk culture.

Ethnoculture provides students with in-depth knowledge of all aspects based on modern requirements, and a universal worldview is formed in them. By implementing such factors as spiritual and educational activities, their feelings of love and respect for the Motherland, respect for national values and traditions are strengthened. As a result, historical freedom, understanding of the spirit of independence, appreciation of national spirituality are strengthened among students.

Ethnocultural competence is the knowledge and understanding of the origin of a nation, its culture, lifestyle, spiritual and educational characteristics, which have flourished in historical processes and are developing to this day. The term ethnoculture consists of two words, a combination of the words ethno and culture. Ethno is Greek for nation, people, and at the same time, it refers to a certain people or nation. This expression represents the origin of a nation, i.e. ethnogenesis. It is possible to understand the origin of the Uzbek people, their ethnic origin, clan and lineage. At the same time, the word ethnos is used in many scientific and theoretical sources.

To explain to the students the historical formation of our people, the stages of its spiritual and educational development, the achievements of our national culture in the past, the meaning and essence of the concepts of people, people, and nation, which have been formed and developed at a certain level in the past and in the present. Ethnocultural competence is also part of teaching the historical process of our future national culture.

Ethnocultural competence is a national-psychological characteristic of a representative of each nation and is classified by the following factors: Cognitive - a person's perfect knowledge of the culture, values, traditions, rules of conduct, traditions of his nation. Having an idea about the similarities and differences between the cultures of other nations. Mastering one's native language, being able to perform actions specific to the national mentality.

Etiquette - to know the moral standards appropriate to the national culture, especially to understand the importance of following the value of "respecting the elders and honoring the children" in the Uzbek nation, and acquiring the skills to adapt to the culture of other nations. Being able to control one's emotions in interaction with representatives of other nationalities.

The need for motivational-cultural communication. Knowing and following the rules of etiquette of other nations. Understanding and accepting the value and culture of other nations. Having a positive attitude towards representatives of other nations and their culture, having knowledge and imagination about their values and traditions. To understand the history of the culture of sister nations and the mutual proximity of the culture of the Uzbek nation. Based on the ethno-cultural

commonality, it consists in acquiring the skill of being able to enter into mutual communication.

In conclusion, it should be noted that the development of ethnocultural competence in students can be achieved by instilling in the minds of students the valuable knowledge of the past of each nation, how it is passed on to the next generation, and the future directly from historical events. It is appropriate to use educational materials, videos, and historical-artistic works related to the achievements of our ancestors during the period of historical evolution in the formation of ethnocultural competence in students. Information about the cultural and educational heritage, national values, traditions, and customs of our people is provided through spiritual events, creative circles and various contests. We would not be wrong to say that getting acquainted with artistic works infused with moral lessons of our nation will further develop the sense of patriotism in students.

On the basis of the listed points, it can be concluded that the formation of ethnocultural competence appears directly on the basis of the student's individual characteristics, interests, personal desires and wishes. It is necessary to take into account the ethnic interest and inclination of the students, and professional competence is also developed at the basis of it. Ensuring interdependence between them ensures the success of future pedagogues in higher pedagogical education. Students are also taught the responsibility of achieving success.

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